

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF RESIN TRANSFER MOLD FILLING PROCESS

M. K. Kang and W. I. Lee
Department of Mechanical Engineering
Seoul National University, Seoul, Korea

and

T. W. Kim, B. S. Kim and E.-J. Jun
Korea Institute of Machinery and Metals
Changwon, Kyungnam, Korea

ABSTRACT

Mold filling process during RTM was simulated numerically using modified Control Volume Finite Element Method (CV-FEM) along with Flow Analysis Network (FAN) method to handle problems associated with the moving resin front. Imaginary new nodes were placed at the intersections between the triangular element border and the flow front. Since the values of pressure at these newly added "imaginary" nodes are expressed in terms of those at the "real" nodes, the "imaginary" nodes do not affect the size of the global matrices. In order to illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed scheme, the mold filling with air bubbles trapped inside were simulated. The shape of the interface was found to be smoother and the change in the pressure near the flow front seems more realistic. The solution accuracy was proven to be considerably higher compared to the conventional method for the same number of nodal points and elements, without significant increase in the computation time.

INTRODUCTION

Resin transfer molding is a process in which resin is injected into a mold preloaded with fibrous reinforcement (Figure 1). It is crucial for the mechanical properties that complete impregnation of the fiber is accomplished. If the location of the resin injection port is not selected properly, dry spots may result. The productivity of this process is directly related to the time required for the resin injection and subsequent curing. In order to reduce the time required, one of the widely used practice is using a heated die. If the resin is heated, the viscosity decreases and thus the flow is enhanced. Furthermore, curing reaction starts taking place during mold filling and reduces the time required for curing. However, if the resin temperature is raised too much, gel point may be reached before the completion of the filling process. Since the mold geometry generally is complicated, relationship between the resin flow and the process variables cannot be obtained analytically.

Numerical simulations have been performed with finite difference method (FDM) using boundary fitted coordinate [1-3] and finite element method (FEM) with moving grids [4-6]. In these techniques, the calculation meshes change every time step as the domain of interest changes. Even though the flow front can be traced precisely, regeneration of the meshes at each time step imposes a great amount of extra computational efforts. In order to circumvent the problem with mesh generation, control volume-finite element method (CV-FEM) [7-9] is widely used. In this numerical scheme, computation is relatively fast due to the fixed finite element mesh, while the exact location of the resin front is difficult to determine. Um and Lee [10] applied boundary element method (BEM) for two dimensional flat mold in which the permeability and the resin viscosity are constant.

The objective of this study is to develop a numerical code to simulate the resin transfer mold filling process. A method is proposed to improve the accuracy of the numerical computation without sacrificing the merits of CV-FEM.

PROBLEM STATEMENT AND GOVERNING EQUATIONS

Consider a mold with a thin cavity loaded with fiber preform. The permeability of the fiber preform may be anisotropic and vary at different locations. The shape of the mold cavity can be a three dimensional shell. Resin is injected at multiple, arbitrary points. The mold is heated to facilitate the resin flow and the curing. The problem is to find out the resin front location, pressure, temperature and degree of cure distributions as functions of time. Because the RTM mold cavity is usually thin, the variation through the thickness is neglected.

The flow of the resin inside the mold through the fiber preform can be assumed to follow the Darcy's law

$$\vec{V} = -\frac{1}{\mu}[K]\nabla P \tag{1}$$

where \vec{V} is the resin velocity, P is the pressure and μ is the resin viscosity. $[K]$ is the permeability tensor for anisotropic porous media and can be a function of location. The mass conservation requires

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{V} = 0 \tag{2}$$

Substituting Eq.(1) into Eq.(2) yields

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\mu}[K]\nabla P\right) = 0 \tag{3}$$

The energy equation must be written separately for the resin and the fiber since energy transfer between these two media exists. However, heat transfer area per unit volume between the fiber and resin is very large due to small fiber diameter. Therefore the fiber and the resin temperatures are taken to be identical except at the flow front. In the region near the resin front, the heat exchange between the fiber and the resin are accounted for using a method described in the following section. Based upon this assumption, the energy conservation becomes

$$\rho c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho_r c_r \vec{V} \cdot \nabla T = \nabla \cdot k \nabla T + (1 - \phi)\dot{G} \tag{4}$$

where T is temperature and t is time. ρ , c and k represent the density, specific heat and thermal conductivity, respectively. f is the fiber volume fraction and the subscript r denote the resin. \dot{G} is the heat generated due to the curing reaction and is written as

$$\dot{G} = H_R \dot{M} \tag{5}$$

where H_R is the heat of reaction and \dot{M} is the rate of the amount of resin cured. The conservation of the chemical species is given by

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} + \frac{\vec{V}}{\phi} \cdot \nabla \alpha = \dot{M} \tag{6}$$

where α is the degree of cure. \dot{M} is given by an empirical relation

$$\dot{M} = (k_1 + k_2 \alpha^m)(1 - \alpha)^n \tag{7}$$

where k_1 , k_2 , m and n are constants which must be obtained from experimental data [10]. The resin viscosity is related to the degree of cure and temperature by

$$\mu = \mu_\infty \exp\left(\frac{\Delta E_\mu}{T} + \kappa \alpha\right) \tag{8}$$

where μ_0 , ΔE_μ and κ are constants which must be determined by experimental data [10].

Boundary conditions can be stated as

Flow Inlet: $P=P_0$ or $V=V_0$; $T=T_0$; $\alpha=0$

Solid Boundary: $dP/dn = 0$ (9)

Free Surface: $P = 0$, $q_{in} = (1-f)\rho_f V_n (T_f - T)$

Here T_f represents the temperature of the fiber.

The solution to Eqs.(1-9) provides the resin front locations and pressure, temperature and degree of cure distributions inside the mold.

NUMERICAL METHOD

By applying the control volume method on the governing equations, a system of algebraic equations can be obtained. First, the mold cavity is divided into a finite number of control volumes. If we integrate the mass conservation equation (Eq.2) with respect to the control volume and apply Green's theorem

$$\int_{cv} \nabla \cdot \vec{V} d\Omega = \int_{cs} \vec{V} \cdot \vec{n} dA \quad (10)$$

where \vec{n} is the vector normal to the control surface. Subscripts CV and CS stand for the control volume and the control surface, respectively. The velocity vector \vec{V} is given by Darcy's law (Eq.2). If we assume that thickness of the mold H is uniform within a control volume, $dA=Hd\Gamma$. Here Γ denotes the perimeter (see Figure 2). Therefore Eq.(10) becomes

$$\int_{cs} H [n_x \quad n_y] \begin{bmatrix} S_{xx} & S_{xy} \\ S_{yx} & S_{yy} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial P}{\partial y} \end{bmatrix} d\Gamma = 0 \quad (11)$$

,where

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_{xx} & S_{xy} \\ S_{yx} & S_{yy} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{H} \int_{-H/2}^{H/2} \frac{1}{\mu} \begin{bmatrix} K_{xx} & K_{xy} \\ K_{yx} & K_{yy} \end{bmatrix} dz \quad (12)$$

n_x and n_y are unit vectors in x and y directions. Applying the same procedure for the energy equation yields

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{cv} \rho c T d\Omega + \int_{cv} \rho_r c_r (u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y}) d\Omega \\ = \int_{cs} k (\frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial T}{\partial z}) d\Gamma + \int_{cv} (1-\phi) H_r (K_1 + K_2 \alpha^m) (1-\alpha)^n d\Omega \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Since the mold cavity is thin, temperature through the thickness can be taken to be uniform. Thus the heat transfer between the mold surface and the composite can be represented by

$$-k \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} = h(T - T_{mold}) \quad (14)$$

where h is the heat transfer coefficient between the mold surface and the composite.

If the conservation equation for the chemical species (Eq.6) is integrated for the control volume, the following equation results

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{cv} \alpha d\Omega + \int_{cv} \frac{1}{\phi} (u \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial y}) d\Omega = \int_{cv} (K_1 + K_2 \alpha^m) (1-\alpha)^n d\Omega \quad (15)$$

The presence of convection term in the conservation equations may result in an oscillation in the numerical solution. This oscillation is called "checker-board" error and becomes common especially when convection is large (high Peclet number). In order to reduce this error, Baliga and Patankar[11] selected a coordinate system oriented in the flow direction.

They used exponential interpolating function in the flow direction and linear interpolating function in the direction perpendicular to the flow. It is proved that exact solution can be obtained with exponential interpolating function in the flow direction for one dimensional flow [12]. In this study, the method proposed by Baliga and Patankar was employed.

As the mold is filled, the calculation domain changes. The control volume method uses fixed grid system. The change in the calculation domain is handled using the following scheme [13, 14]. All the control volumes are divided in three groups according to the fill-up ratio f (see Figure 4). If a control volume is completely filled ($f=1$), it is classified as main flow region. If a control volume is empty ($f=0$), it is called empty region. The control volumes partially filled with resin consist the resin flow front and are called flow front region ($0 < f < 1$). For the flow front region, fluxes across the control surfaces are recorded. The fill-up ratio f for each control volume in the flow front region is updated according to the mass influx. When the fill-up ratio becomes unity for a specific control volume, it become a part of the main flow region.

Since CV-FEM employs fixed grid system, computation is relatively fast while there are some shortcomings originating from using the fixed grid system. The accuracy of the solution is limited by the mesh density regardless of the size of the time increment and the boundary conditions at the free boundary cannot be given to the boundary itself but to the nearest nodal points. The elements at the free boundary are divided by the flow front into two regions. The dividing interface tends to move as the resin fills. However, in the CV/FEM method, only the completely filled ($f=1$) control volumes are considered in the calculation. Therefore, in order to obtain accurate numerical results, the effect of the "floating" interface in the flow front region must be considered.

In this investigation, a new algorithm modifying the conventional CV-FEM is used [15]. In the method employed in this paper, imaginary new nodes are placed at the intersections between the triangular element border and the flow front (l and n in Figure 5b). One more node is located at the midpoint on the third segment of the triangle (m in Figure 5b). The locations of l, m and n are determined by the filled fraction, f of the nodes 1, 2 and 3 by the following equations

$$\begin{aligned} x_l &= \frac{(0.5 - f_1)}{(f_2 - f_1)}(x_2 - x_1) + x_1 & y_l &= \frac{(0.5 - f_1)}{(f_2 - f_1)}(y_2 - y_1) + y_1 \\ x_m &= \frac{(0.5 - f_2)}{(f_3 - f_2)}(x_3 - x_2) + x_2 & y_m &= \frac{(0.5 - f_2)}{(f_3 - f_2)}(y_3 - y_2) + y_2 \\ x_n &= \frac{(0.5 - f_3)}{(f_1 - f_3)}(x_1 - x_3) + x_3 & y_n &= \frac{(0.5 - f_3)}{(f_1 - f_3)}(y_1 - y_3) + y_3 \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where f_1, f_2 and f_3 are the filled fractions at the nodes 1, 2 and 3, respectively. In CV-FEM the flow front is usually located along the line where the interpolated filled fraction is 0.5 [16, 17]. In the above equation, x_l, x_m and x_n are interpolated with the filled fraction at each nodes as weights. If the new triangular elements $1ln, 2ml, 3nm$ and lmn are directly incorporated into the global grid system, the mesh topology should be rearranged with the movement of the flow front, and thus nullify the advantage of employing the fixed grid system. This difficulty can be overcome by expressing the values of pressure at the additional nodes in terms of those at the "real" nodes 1, 2 and 3. To be more specific, consider the mass flux across the line ln (Figure 5b) for example. The mass flux can be expressed in terms of P_1, P_l and P_n and the flow conductance of the subelement $1ln$. This mass flux can also be estimated in terms of P_l, P_n and P_m and the flow conductance of the subelement lmn . Since these two quantities must be identical, we can obtain a relationship between P_l, P_n, P_m and the pressures at the real nodes, P_1, P_2 and P_3 . In the same manner, as the mass fluxes across the line mn and the line lm are considered, two more relationships between the pressure at the imaginary nodes (P_l, P_n, P_m) and the pressure at the real nodes (P_1, P_2, P_3) are obtained. By solving these three equations, P_l, P_n, P_m can be expressed in terms of P_1, P_2, P_3 [15]. Therefore, the newly added "imaginary" nodes do not affect the size of the global matrices and thus do not heavily increase the computation time and memory requirement. It is noted that these advantages are accomplished at the expense of the symmetry in the global stiffness matrix.

According to the numerical scheme described above, a computer code was written. The flow chart of the code is shown in Figure 3. First, the pressure distribution is calculated. The viscosity required for the calculation is taken from the value of the previous time step. From the pressure distribution, resin velocity is calculated using the Darcy's law. For calculations of temperature and degree of cure, smaller time step is used to take into account the non-steady terms. With temperature and degree of cure thus obtained, the value of resin viscosity is estimated. The new viscosity value replaces the old one used to proceed the calculation. The flow front is advanced by updating the filled fraction of each control volume using the resin velocity obtained. For the new calculation domain, this procedure is repeated until the mold is completely filled.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

In order to illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed scheme, the mold filling process during RTM with entrapped air bubbles is considered. In spite of the convenience in the prediction of the flow front, CV-FEM fails to give the most accurate solutions when the nodes are not preferably assigned because the accuracy of the solution is highly dependent on the size and structure of the initially generated mesh. Moreover, CV-FEM cannot give reasonable solutions for problems with complicated flow fronts. For example, the movement of air bubbles trapped inside can be estimated with a reasonable accuracy only with a huge number of computational grids. In Figure 6, calculated pressure distributions at different times are shown. The air entrapped in the bubble is assumed to follow the ideal gas equation of state. In this example, resin is injected from the inlet located at the center (see Figure 6a). Since there is only one vent provided at the upper left corner, air is trapped at the lower half of the mold. As the mold is filled, the air bubble undergoes a compression (Figure 6b). Since there is no air vent installed at the upper right corner, another air bubble is formed (Figure 6c). The two bubbles are independently compressed, and it is observed that the second bubble migrates toward the air vent (Figure 6c). Unlike the results from conventional CV-FEM with the same mesh density, the shape of the interface is smoother and the change in the pressure near the flow front seems more realistic. The mass conservation both for the resin and the air are satisfied.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

A computer code was developed for numerical simulation of mold filling process in RTM using modified CV-FEM. The proposed scheme allows a refinement of the elements at the flow front for more accurate solution without severe increase in the computational effort. In order to illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed scheme, mold filling process during RTM with entrapped air bubbles is considered. The solution accuracy is proven to be considerably higher compared to that of the conventional method for the same number of nodal points and elements. The computer code developed in this study should be appropriate in predicting the process variables and thus aids in the design of the mold and process conditions.

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Material properties of resin

$$\mu_w = 5.419 \times 10^{-5} \text{ Pa} \cdot \text{s}$$

$$\frac{\Delta E}{R} = 3636.45$$

$$\kappa = 26.89$$

$$A_1 = 2.081 \times 10^8, \quad A_2 = 3.406 \times 10^9$$

$$\frac{E_1}{R} = -10048.4$$

$$\frac{E_2}{R} = -9505.58$$

$$m_1 = 0.693, \quad m_2 = 1.327$$

$$T_0 = 100^\circ \text{C}$$

$$C_1 = 0.02639, \quad C_2 = -8.8466$$

$$\rho_r = 1030 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

$$c_r = 1900 \text{ J/kg} \cdot \text{K}$$

$$k_r = 0.193 \text{ W/m} \cdot \text{K}$$

Material properties of fiber

$$K_{xx} = K_{yy} = 3.95 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2$$

$$\rho_f = 2540 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

$$c_f = 835 \text{ J/kg} \cdot \text{K}$$

$$k_f = 0.76 \text{ W/m} \cdot \text{K}$$

Table 1. Material properties used in the numerical simulation

Figure 1. Resin Transfer Molding Process

Figure 2. Definition sketch of a control volume

Figure 3. Flow chart of the numerical scheme

Figure 4. Classification of the nodes into three groups, namely, empty nodes, flow front nodes and interior nodes

Figure 5. Comparison of the proposed modification to the conventional CVFEM

Figure 6. Simulation of mold filling considering the possible trap and movement of the air bubbles